

Analysis of the solidification and phase separation of calcium chloride hexahydrate with different water content by means of X-ray computed tomography

Dario Guarda^{a,*}, Jorge Martinez-Garcia^b, Benjamin Fenk^b, Poppy O'Neill^b, Rebecca Ravotti^b, Damian Gwerder^b, Anastasia Stamatiou^b, Jörg Worlitschek^b, Simone Mancin^a, Philipp Schuetz^b

^a Department of Management and Engineering, University of Padova, Vicenza 36100, Italy

^b Competence Centre for Thermal Energy Storage, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, 6048 Horw, Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

X-ray computed tomography (XCT) is a well-known technology that is quite new to the field of research of non-metallic phase change materials (PCMs) employed in latent thermal energy storages (LTESs). The current work demonstrate the value of XCT, opening unprecedented opportunities to obtain new insights on solid-liquid phase transition. XCT permits to measure accurately volumetric liquid fraction, observing the formation of voids and phase separation, also known as segregation, which is hindering the deployment of salt hydrates, a particular class of PCMs known for their relatively low cost compared to their quite high volumetric energy density. The capabilities of XCT could eventually lead to the understanding of the segregation phenomenon of salt hydrates and in the future, reliable salt hydrates-based LTES will be able to support the energy transition.

In the current study, the potential of XCT is shown during the analysis of calcium chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$). XCT accuracy and rigorous protocol make it a potential benchmark for new measurement technologies.

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Figures

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: dario.guarda@unipd.it (D. Guarda).

X-ray parameters

Acceleration voltage (kV)	160
Current (μA)	156
Power (W)	24.96
Filter	1.0 mm Al
Focus type	High Power

Detector parameters

Amplification capacity (pF)	8
Pixel binning	1×1
Frame binning	4
Integration time (ms)	170

Scan parameters

Single scan	
Number of projections	400
Scan time (hh:mm:ss)	00:04:54
Average time in between scans (min)	6

Reconstruction parameters

Reconstructed image dimensions (pixel)	$400 \times 400 \times 1516$
Voxel size (mm)	0.103
Beam hardening correction	4

Manipulator parameter

Source Object Distance SOD (mm)	410
Source Detector Distance SDD (mm)	600
Magnification (-)	1.46

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dario Guarda: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jorge Martinez-Garcia:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Benjamin Fenk:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Poppy O'Neill:** Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Rebecca Ravotti:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Damian Gwerder:** Supervision, Data curation. **Anastasia Stamatou:** Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Jörg Worlitschek:** Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Simone Mancin:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Philipp Schuetz:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Further reading

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